

Sustainability and Recycling Pathways in Photovoltaic Energy Systems

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Abstract - With the climate change and continuous development of the sustainable energy industry the Solar photovoltaic technology has become increasingly popular among world energy generation and storage sector. With around 30-year life span of photovoltaic modules, by 2050 it has been predicted to get nearly 78 million ton of solar panel waste. When moving towards recycling of photovoltaic systems it is crucial to identify the most effective method to use on different steps. Based on secondary data analysis, this research follows a qualitative research approach. With the help of available literature, analysis is done considering the factors such as Technology readiness level (TRL), environment impacts, process complexity, recovery efficiency and energy consumption. According to the material recovery goal, regional policy frameworks and infrastructure availability, the most suitable recycling method has yet to be decided. Therefore, throughout this analysis, the need of the multi-technological recycling industry is highlighted to move towards a sustainable photovoltaic life cycle. However, there are various new possibilities available to increase the progress of recycling. Integrating characteristics of circular design into photovoltaic modules like modular architectures and reversible encapsulants will make future recycling easier. Overall, this paper clarifies that, for a circular and sustainable photovoltaic technology, a complex and interconnected approach is needed rather than isolated technologies or policies.

Keywords - Photovoltaic, Solar, Recycling, Circular, Sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The sun's radiation is the main source of life and energy which we experience on earth. When it comes to directly harnessing the sun energy to create electricity, solar photovoltaic technology plays a major role. During a decade back since year 2022, from 104 to 1053 gigawatt increase in photovoltaic system installation have been seen and it is approximately 90% increment [1]. Researchers have predicted that approximately 2840 gigawatts of worldwide solar capacity will reach by 2030 and it will increase to 8650 gigawatts by 2050 [2]. Most of the photovoltaic systems available today are not planned to go through recycling process and that have become increasing environmental concern, therefore it has been identified that introducing recycling steps to currently available "take-make-use-dispose" linear model is essential to go toward sustainable and circular industry [3]. After near 30-year lifetime of photovoltaic modules, it has been identified three crucial situations to consider as, 1) disposal to landfills 2) recycling by Limited glass recycling facilities 3) recycling by full recovery of end-of-life photovoltaics [4]. Disposing photovoltaic module to

landfills have been identified as the most common out of above three situations while other to have considerable benefits. Furthermore, when moving towards a circular economy while mitigating the harmful effect of the photovoltaic industry, it is crucial to consider end of life management practices in every stage of the photovoltaic system such as design, production, operation and decommissioning. With the help of already available publications, such as policy document and technical reports on photovoltaic energy system related recycling and sustainability Pathways, a comprehensive interpretation, synthesis and comparison have been done in this research. Furthermore, while keeping sustainability matrices like Greenhouse gas (GHG) emission, energy payback time (EPBT) and energy return on investment (EROI) as comparison parameter, an analysis on basic stages of photovoltaic system's life cycle such as acquisition of materials, module manufacturing, installation, operation and end of life management have been done throughout this research.

II. METHODOLOGY

Based on several sources, this analysis has been done and the reason for choosing those documents can be mentioned as, direct reliability to sustainability and recycling of photovoltaic systems, technical depth and credibility of Peer reviews. For the purpose of rating the recycling effectiveness and sustainability performance of a photovoltaic system with the help of published documents, an evaluation framework has been created. With comparison of recycling Pathways such as advanced hybrid, thermal, mechanical and chemical processes with respect to technology readiness level(TRL), requirements of process energy, rate of material recovery and complexity of the operations, technical performance have been analysed [5] [6] [7] [8] [9]. When it comes to evaluation of environmental impacts, it is carried out mainly with the help of life cycle analysis, however other factors such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emission, energy payback time (EPBT) and energy return on investment are also considered [10] [11] [12].

When integrating policy considerations, sustainability metrics and recycling Pathways towards collected circular photovoltaic system design, given conceptual framework assists as an analytical and visual model. By comparing and plotting the details in journal articles [13] [14] [15] [16] against the basic stages of the photovoltaic life cycle which

are acquisition of raw materials, manufacturing of photovoltaic modules, installation, operation and management of the end of life, this process has been done. In the middle of this diagram a feedback loop can be found which represents the collected materials at the recycling process that re-contributes to the manufacturing of photovoltaic modules while reducing the extraction of natural resources and environmental impacts [5] [8] [9] [17]. Within this framework, placement of each recycling path is done by the technical data related to technology readiness level, recovery efficiency and energy inputs. Furthermore, the order of the importance of each path is calculated by the sustainability indicators like Greenhouse gas emissions, energy payback time and energy return on investment [10] [11] [12] [18]. Moreover, for the purpose of strengthening the clarity, a policy layer is included in this framework, with regulatory mechanisms such as eco designs standards, extended producer responsibilities schemes and landfill bans [19]. With these methods This Framework can illustrate practical feasibility and alignment of the governance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the circular economy conceptual model, all the stages of the photovoltaic life cycle such as material extraction, manufacturing process, installation, operation and end of life recycling have been properly analysed, so that it is possible to suggest options for re-inclusion of recycled materials. Inside the conceptual model, the sources of inputs have been categorized into three main parts as primary resources, secondary resources and auxiliary inputs. Under primary sources all the virgin materials are categorized and for the secondary resources, recovered materials from the recycling process have been included and auxiliary inputs are described as inputs such as water, necessary Chemicals and energy. The main focus of the conceptual model is to increase the use of secondary resources while reducing the consumption of primary resources and auxiliary inputs to minimize the financial and environmental footprint [20] [21].

Basics of design for recycling (DFR) such as junction boxes that can easily separate and encapsulant consisting reversible adhesion properties have been embodied in the manufacturing step. With the basics of designed for recycling, efficiency of the recovery in mechanical and hybrid recycling methods can be increased without any follow up process [15] [2]. Moreover, with inclusion of product passports such as maintaining digital records related to instructions for recycling and the composition of the materials, helps to increase the efficiency of recovery process [22].

When considering the Optimization methods, the end-of-life stage has to be created as a template that decides the most suitable recycling method out of mechanical, thermal, chemical and hybrid method, depending on the used technology, recovery goals and physical condition of the photovoltaic modules. To improve this further, machine learning and artificial intelligent based sorting methods can be used. [2] [23].

Recycle materials are directed into specific circularity stages such as, aluminium and glass are sent to secondary manufacturing and high value materials like silver and silicon wafer which are recovered in near perfect conditions are redirected to the photovoltaic manufacturing process. To ensure the circularity of the process without a need of any outside involvement or additional resources, practices such as maintaining regional reprocessing plants, managing timely supply chain and minimizing emissions that happened during transportation, are used [6] [16] [17].

Photovoltaic industry related directives and market techniques such as mandate related to recycled materials, extended producer responsibility (EPR) and recycling plants, are included in the conceptual framework of the circular economy. These directives motivate photovoltaic manufacturers to absorb various designs for recycling (DFR) techniques and to increase recycling, quantitatively. Furthermore, with standardization methods related to performance and origin, trust of the interested parties were uplifted and therefore industrial demand for recycled photovoltaic material has been increased [24] [19] [2].

In this circular economy conceptual framework, life cycle assessment is included as a feedback loop so that parameters such as recovery efficiency, energy payback time and greenhouse gas emissions, can be analysed as soon as they are recorded. Through this, continuous development of recycling and manufacturing processes can be done, while updating the system according to the changing industrial demands and new technologies [10] [12]

When considering the recycling methods, it has been clear that none of the recycling methods is individually capable of achieving the circularity in photovoltaic life cycle. Mechanical recycling method is the most economical recycling method but when it comes to recovery of silicon for semiconductor reuse, it is not considered as a very efficient method [13] [6]. Even with the already available advantages such as low energy consumption, strong infrastructure availability and scalability, mechanical recycling method is unable to achieve circularity due to inability of recovering high purity silicon wafer or silver which affects the greenhouse gas emission and energy payback time of the photovoltaic life cycle [5] [25]

The thermal recycling method is capable of recovering some amount of silicon and silver, however there can be some energy management problems [8] [20]. While improving the recovery quality and energy payback time, thermal recycling method have been able to dissolve encapsulant layer and release silicon wafer and silver in a considerably good condition [13] [2] [7]. But as the name suggest, thermal recycling method involved with high temperature processing and energy demand, therefore it is required to maintain necessary 'off gas treatment' and process management techniques to avoid environmental hazards [8] [26]. Therefore, it is clear that thermal recycling method have overcome some challenges that are present in mechanical recycling method, however the scalability of thermal recycling is present due to the requirement of high level of energy and environment hazard management techniques [27] [20]

Chemical recycling method can be identified as the most successful method of material recovery, but when it is performed on a large scale there is a risk of various environmental hazards [17] [9]. Even under the experimentation level, chemical recycling method have been able to reach almost perfect sustainable and circular photovoltaic life cycle, by recovering silicon wafer and silver in high purity levels [14] [3] [19]. However, in an industrial level application, it has a low level of technology readiness levels due to chemical handling risks, higher operating costs and reagent recovery boundaries [10] [11]

By mitigating all those limitations hybrid recycling method is introduced, however it still happens in a very controlled environment due to lack of industrial level adaptations [7] [19]. Objectives of circular economy such as material purity, adaptability of the process and high levels of recovery yields have been able to achieved through hybrid recycling system [17] [9]. Therefore, according to the material recovery goal, regional policy frameworks and infrastructure availability, the most suitable recycling method has yet to be decided [22].

IV. CONCLUSION

The main focus of this thesis has been, to evaluate the recycling pathways and sustainability of photovoltaic systems, while analysing the performance of presently available recycling Technologies, adherence to sustainability matrix and implementations with in circular economy framework [15] [16] [1]. Through gathering various perceptions from analysis of policies, studies related to life cycle assessment and academic publications related to technical details, this research gives strong analysis on the pathways to move from linearity towards circularity and resource efficient life cycle [5] [24] [25]. In the point of view of sustainability, adapting recycling technologies into photovoltaic systems has been helpful in minimizing problems related to air pollution and energy spent inside the life cycle [19] [4]. Moreover, out of all the recycling methods chemical and hybrid recycling have been identified as two Methods that can achieve the highest amount of advantages [15] [16] [10]. Primarily these two recycling methods help to maintain circularity by recovering precious materials and sending them back to the photovoltaic module manufacturing process. Through this, consumption of virgin resources and photovoltaic waste that end up in landfills get reduced. With the help of suggested conceptual model, supportive policy frameworks, design for recycling basics and loops of material integration can be joined together to generate a circular and sustainable photovoltaic industry [21] [18]. Through this research, it has been able to gather available technologies, limitations and propose a futuristic model to help in future policy making and research.

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